

Walter Benjamin Program: Final Report

Hyperpolarization of water from UV radicals to
study water dynamics around proteins

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1 General information

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Hyperpolarization of water from UV radicals to study water dynamics around proteins

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Technical Reporting period (entire funding period):

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2 Summary

English:

This project aimed to advance hyperpolarized water (HyperW) as a practical and broadly applicable sensitivity booster for biomolecular NMR by using UV-generated, thermally unstable radicals to produce radical-free hyperpolarized solutions with long liquid-state lifetimes and simplified handling. The work followed two connected objectives: (i) developing and applying multidimensional UV-HyperW NMR workflows to obtain residue-specific hydration readouts in a model protein system (CI2), including discrimination between chemical exchange and transfer mediated by structural water; and (ii) establishing the basis for transportable, long-lived solid-state UV-HyperW to enable high-field experiments on larger biomolecules at remote NMR facilities.

The first objective was achieved. UV-HyperW was established as a routine workflow for protein NMR under the conditions used here, enabling rapid acquisition of 2D correlation spectra after injection without the need for pressurized transfers. By systematically varying pH, the experiments spanned a broad range of water–amide exchange regimes. Comparison with CLEANEX-PM enabled an operational “HyperW-positive/CLEANEX-negative” residue signature, which isolated amide sites reporting on conserved internal structural water in CI2 in a single, rapid 2D readout.

The second objective (transportable UV-HyperW and application to large biomolecules) was not reached within the funding period. Solid-state radical quenching without prohibitive losses of ^1H polarization proved substantially more challenging than anticipated. However, the project delivered a key advance by resolving a previously hidden multispecies radical network in UV-irradiated pyruvic acid (PA). The identification and kinetic/thermal characterization of at least four radical species provides a mechanistic basis for understanding radical persistence and for guiding future optimization strategies relevant to both dissolution performance and solid-state quenching.

German:

Dieses Projekt hatte das Ziel, hyperpolarisiertes Wasser (HyperW) als praktischen und breit einsetzbaren Sensitivitäts-Booster für biomolekulare NMR voranzubringen. Dazu wurden UV-erzeugte, thermisch instabile Radikale genutzt, um radikalfreie hyperpolarisierte Lösungen mit langen Lebensdauern im flüssigen Zustand zu erzeugen, welche dadurch die insgesamt Handhabung des Experimentes vereinfachen. Die Arbeit verfolgte zwei miteinander verknüpfte Ziele. Zum einen, die Entwicklung und Anwendung multidimensionaler UV-HyperW-NMR-Arbeitsabläufe, um in dem Modell-Proteinsystem (CI2) das Ablesen von proteinrest-

abhängigen Hydratations-Signalmustern zu ermöglichen. Ziel war hier außerdem die Unterscheidung zwischen Signalverstärkung mittels chemischen Austausches und einem durch strukturelles Wasser vermittelten Polarisationstransfer. Zum anderen, die Schaffung der Grundlage für transportables, langlebiges UV-HyperW im Festkörper, um Hochfeld-Experimente an größeren Biomolekülen an entfernten NMR-Einrichtungen zu ermöglichen.

Das erste Ziel wurde erreicht. UV-HyperW wurde unter den hier verwendeten Bedingungen als Routine-Workflow für Protein-NMR etabliert und ermöglichte die schnelle Aufnahme von 2D-Korrelationsspektren nach der Injektion, ohne dass Probentransfers unter Druck erforderlich waren. Durch systematische Variation des pH-Wertes wurden die Experimente über ein breites Spektrum von Wasser–Amid-Austauschregimen hinweg durchgeführt. Der Vergleich mit CLEANEX-PM erlaubte eine klare „HyperW-positiv/CLEANEX-negativ“-Residuen-Signatur, die in einem einzigen, schnellen 2D-Readout Amid-Positionen isolierte, welche in Cl2 konserviertes, internes, strukturelles Wasser anzeigen

Das zweite Ziel (transportables UV-HyperW und Anwendung auf große Biomoleküle) wurde innerhalb der Förderperiode nicht erreicht. Die Radikal-Eliminierung im Festkörper ohne signifikante und dadurch unerschwingliche Verluste der ^1H -Polarisation erwies sich als deutlich herausfordernder als erwartet. Dennoch lieferte das Projekt einen zentralen Fortschritt, indem ein zuvor verborgenes Multispezies-Radikalnetzwerk in UV-bestrahlter Brenztraubensäure (PA) aufgeklärt wurde. Die Identifizierung sowie die kinetische und thermische Charakterisierung von mindestens vier Radikalspezies bietet eine mechanistische Grundlage zum Verständnis der Radikalpersistenz und einen Ansatz künftiger Optimierungsstrategien, die sowohl für die Polarisierung während der Dissolution erhöhen als auch für das Eliminieren der Radikale im Festkörper relevant sind.

3 Scientific Progress Report

Water molecules are integral components of biomolecular systems, contributing to structure stabilization and functional tuning, yet they remain difficult to observe directly in liquid solution with residue specificity.¹⁻⁴ Classical solution-state NMR approaches to hydration (e.g., NOESY/ROESY) can in principle distinguish dipolar transfer from chemical exchange, but in practice are often limited by sensitivity and acquisition time when targeting weak or transient hydration contacts under native-like conditions.^{5, 6}

The goal of this project was therefore to advance hyperpolarized water (HyperW)⁷ as an accessible sensitivity booster for multidimensional biomolecular NMR, specifically leveraging

UV-generated, thermally unstable radicals that enable radical-free hyperpolarized solutions after dissolution and hence long liquid-state lifetimes.⁸

The project pursued two connected objectives:

- (i) establishing multidimensional UV-HyperW protein NMR workflows and using them to obtain residue-specific hydration readouts in the model protein chymotrypsin inhibitor 2 (CI2), including a discrimination between chemical exchange and transfer mediated by structural water
- (ii) enabling transportable, long-lived UV-HyperW for high-field experiments on larger biomolecules via solid-state lifetime extension and radical quenching strategies.

These objectives were implemented through four work packages (WPs): WP1 Multidimensional UV-HyperW in CI2, WP2 Quantitative/diagnostic hydration readouts and structural-water identification in CI2, WP3 Towards transportable UV-HyperW via polarizing-agent/sample optimization and radical-quenching concepts, and WP4 Application to larger biomolecules at high field.

Description of the project-specific results and findings

WP1/WP2: Multidimensional UV-HyperW workflows and residue-specific hydration readouts in CI2 (achieved).

A central deliverable of the project was the establishment and application of a radical-free UV-HyperW workflow for biomolecular NMR. UV irradiation of frozen pyruvic acid (PA)-based samples produced high radical concentrations enabling fast DNP buildup ($\geq 65\%$ within 60 minutes under the conditions reported). Upon dissolution, the radicals recombined into diamagnetic species, yielding radical-free hyperpolarized water with high liquid-state polarization ($>30\%$ ^1H) and long relaxation times (>60 s in neat HyperW at 40°C ; $30\text{--}40$ s upon injection into protein solutions under the conditions used). This combination enabled rapid acquisition of 2D protein correlation spectra after injection while preserving spectral resolution.

To connect HyperW signal transfer to hydration processes and distinguish mechanisms, the project implemented systematic pD variation spanning regimes from slow amide–water exchange (low pD) to fast exchange (high pD). In CI2, HyperW-enhanced SOFAST HMQC⁹ spectra provided residue-specific enhancement patterns across this pD range.

A key methodological result is the combined use of HyperW with CLEANEX-PM¹⁰, which

selectively reports signals arising from chemical exchange with water at thermal equilibrium by suppressing through-space transfer during the mixing period. This enabled an operational and residue-specific classification: a subset of resonances was identified that were HyperW-positive but CLEANEX-negative, indicating that their enhancement cannot be explained by fast chemical exchange alone.

In CI2, this “HyperW-positive/CLEANEX-negative” signature isolated four amides linked to crystallographically conserved internal waters¹¹ in a single rapid 2D readout after injection. The mechanistic interpretation supported by the experimental observations is magnetization transfer via exchange-relayed NOE through long-residence structural water, consistent with structural-water exchange occurring on timescales sufficient to mediate transfer under the experimental conditions.

Overall, WP1/WP2 were completed in line with the project plan: UV-HyperW was established as a routine multidimensional approach for hydration readouts and enabled a practical structural-water signature in a benchmark protein system, with clear linkage between pD-dependent exchange behavior and the identification of conserved internal hydration sites. This is reported in the publication: Hecker, F., Teilum, K., Capozzi, A., Lerche, M. H.: Residue-Specific Signatures of Structural Water Identified by Dissolution Dynamic Nuclear Polarization with UV-Generated Radicals, *Angew. Chem. Intl. Ed.* **2026**, accepted.

WP3: Radical chemistry and implications for quenching/transportability (partially achieved via mechanistic advance).

WP3 aimed to produce transportable HyperW to enable hyperpolarized NMR experiments at sites without polarizers. This aim was dependent on the elimination of all radicals in the solid state, as proton solid state relaxation times are particularly sensitive to the presence of paramagnetic species. During the funding period, the project produced a major mechanistic advance by resolving the radical composition of UV-irradiated pyruvic acid: rather than a single, previously reported ketyl species,^{12, 13} EPR and isotope-labeling-based analysis demonstrated a multispecies radical network with at least four distinct radicals showing different buildup kinetics and thermal stability.

This result provides a concrete basis for understanding radical persistence and for guiding future optimization of UV-radical precursors and quenching concepts, including the suppression of relaxation-relevant side products and more rational control of the solid-state radical population. The work is also placed in the broader context of pyruvic-acid

photochemistry that underpins UV radical generation.¹⁴ This is reported in the publication Hecker, F., Capozzi, A., Lerche, M. H.: Uncovering a Multispecies Radical Network in UV-Irradiated Pyruvic Acids, *J. Phys. Chem. Let.* **2026**, under review.

WP4: Application to larger biomolecules at high field (not achieved).

WP4 depended on successful completion of WP3 (transportable UV-HyperW with sufficiently preserved polarization). Because solid-state quenching without excessive ¹H polarization loss was not achieved within the funding period, transported UV-HyperW experiments for large biomolecules and TROSY-type proof-of-principle studies could not be carried out as planned.

Handling of Research Data

The project generated new spectroscopic measurement data on chemical compounds and biomolecules using EPR, NMR, and DNP. No data from previous projects was reused. The data comprise raw instrument outputs, processed spectra, fit/simulation results, and analysis/visualization scripts used for publication figures and derived parameters, in total approximately 100 GB total, comprising more than 800 distinct datasets, in some cases containing multiple sub-experiments.

Formats: EPR (.xml, .csv), NMR (TopSpin format, .csv), DNP (RS2D format, .csv), processing/analysis (MATLAB .m/.mat, Python .py, MestReNova .mnova).

Documentation and data quality: Experimental procedures and sample preparation were documented in laboratory notebooks; during the project an electronic lab notebook (ELN) was implemented to strengthen traceability. Spectroscopic datasets were linked to samples and experiments using sequential sample and experiment IDs embedded in file names.

Quality assurance: Data quality was supported through replicate measurements and script-based processing (spectral fitting and simulation) to ensure consistency between raw spectra, processed spectra, and reported results. Decisions on fit/simulation acceptance were not separately logged beyond the resulting outputs.

Software: ESR Studio 1.74.2 (EPR), TopSpin 4.2 (NMR), SpinIt 2023.09 (DNP), MATLAB

2024b, Python 3, and MestReNova 14.1.1 (analysis/processing). No dedicated reproducible runtime environment (e.g., containers) was created; reproducibility is ensured by depositing primary data and the scripts used.

Storage and technical archiving during the project: All spectroscopic data and documentation were stored within the group's lab book/ELN workflow and backed up via institutional cloud and ownCloud. Automatic weekly backups were used for the primary data storage. Manual weekly backups were performed for analysis scripts and personal working data. The project did not generate sensitive personal data; access was managed through institutional accounts and group-controlled storage permissions.

Legal obligations and conditions: The data do not involve humans or animals; therefore, no ethics approvals or special regulatory constraints applied. Data and code were published without third-party restrictions. Ownership and reuse conditions are clarified via repository publication and licensing.

Data exchange and long-term accessibility: For publications, all primary data and analysis scripts were deposited in Zenodo with a DOI cited in the manuscripts. The dataset is released under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0) and was openly available upon submission (no embargo). The released package prioritizes reuse by including raw measurement data, processed outputs, and the scripts needed to reproduce the reported analyses and figures.

Responsibilities and resources: All project researchers were responsible for accurate documentation (lab book), consistent file naming with sample/experiment IDs, and maintaining analysis scripts. Final curation and Zenodo deposition (including README preparation) were handled by the corresponding author of the associated publications. The corresponding author serves as the long-term contact for questions and reuse support. Resource needs were primarily staff time for documentation, routine backup, and final dataset curation for public release.

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

Hecker, F., Capozzi, A., Lerche, M. H.: Uncovering a Multispecies Radical Network in UV-Irradiated Pyruvic Acids, *J. Phys. Chem. Let.* **2026**, under review.

Hecker, F., Teilum, K., Capozzi, A., Lerche, M. H.: Residue-Specific Signatures of Structural Water Identified by Dissolution Dynamic Nuclear Polarization with UV-Generated Radicals, *Angew. Chem. Intl. Ed.* **2026**, accepted, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202523739>.

Lenjer, M., Schwieger, L., Tkach, I., Hecker, F., Bennati, M.: “Mims Electron-Nuclear Double Resonance (ENDOR) with chirp microwave pulses”, *J. Magn. Res.* **2026**, 382, 108005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmr.2025.108005>.

Lenjer, M., Wili, N., Hecker, F., Bennati, M.: “Electron spin dynamics during microwave pulses studied by 94 GHz chirp and phase-modulated EPR experiments”, *Magn. Reson.* **2025**, 6, 43–75, <https://doi.org/10.5194/mr-6-43-2025>.

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

Poster ‘Hyperpolarized water via UV-generated radicals for protein studies’ at the 45th FGMR (Fachgruppe Magnetische Resonanz, GdCH) annual discussion meeting in Rostock, DE.

Oral + Poster Presentation ‘Hyperpolarized water via UV-generated radicals to study the

hydration of proteins' at the Linderstrøm-Lang Centre for Protein Research symposium 2024 in Copenhagen, DK.

Oral Presentation 'Hyperpolarized Water via UV-Generated Radicals to Study the Hydration of Proteins' at the joint ISMAR-ENC conference 2025 in Asilomar, USA receiving a JMR/JMRO award.